

Passive Transfer Immunity in Calves: From Colostrum Management to Practical Strategies^A

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Abstract: Passive transfer immunity (PTI) is a critical determinant of health and survival in neonatal calves, as they are born with an immature immune system and depend entirely on colostrum immunoglobulins for early immune protection. Failure of passive transfer (FPT), commonly defined as a serum IgG concentration below 1000 mg dL⁻¹ at 24 - 48 hours of age, remains a widespread problem worldwide and is associated with increased morbidity, mortality, and reduced growth performance. This review summarizes the fundamental principles and practical aspects of successful passive transfer management. Colostrum management, including quality, quantity, and timing of feeding, is the primary determinant of PTI success. High-quality colostrum (≥ 50 g L⁻¹ IgG; Brix $\geq 22 - 23$ %) should be administered as early as possible after birth, ideally within the first 2 hours of life. Calves should receive approximately 3 - 4 L of colostrum at first feeding, followed by a second feeding within the first 8 - 12 hours to ensure sufficient immunoglobulin intake. PTI status is typically evaluated between 24 and 48 hours after birth, with 48 hours considered the most reliable time point. Direct measurement of serum IgG using radial immunodiffusion (RID) or ELISA remains the gold standard; however, practical on-farm tools such as serum total protein and Brix refractometry are widely used for routine monitoring. In herds with a high prevalence of FPT, systematic evaluation of colostrum management practices and calf-related factors such as dystocia, hypoxia, and metabolic acidosis is required. Optimizing colostrum management and routinely monitoring passive transfer are key strategies to improve calf health and herd productivity.

Keywords: Neonatal calf, Passive transfer immunity, Colostrum

^A The study does not require approval from an ethics committee. The article has been prepared according to research and publication ethics.

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Introduction

Sustainable and successful cattle production depend fundamentally on raising healthy calves, as the continuity of cattle populations is directly tied to calf survival and early-life development. Despite its importance, neonatal calf diseases and mortality remain major health challenges in cattle production systems worldwide. Several factors influence calf health, including infectious agents, environmental and hygienic conditions, and colostrum management. Among these, inadequate hygiene and poor environmental conditions can increase pathogen exposure, thereby elevating the risk of disease in neonatal calves, particularly when colostrum feeding is insufficient or delayed (Weaver et al., 2000; Raboisson et al., 2013; Hyde et al., 2020).

In cattle, due to the epitheliochorial structure of the placenta, immunoglobulins are not sufficiently transferred from the dam to the fetus during pregnancy, and calves are born agammaglobulinemic or hypogammaglobulinemic. Therefore, the acquisition of immunity after birth depends entirely on colostrum intake (McGuirk and Collins, 2004; Blum, 2006; Topal et al., 2018).

Colostrum, produced in the mammary glands during the first three days postpartum, is a complex biological fluid containing dozens of biologically active components, including immunoglobulins (especially IgG), vitamins, minerals, growth factors such as epidermal growth factor (EGF), insulin-like growth factor-1 [IGF-1], transforming growth factor- β 1 (TGF- β 1), TGF- β 2, fibroblast growth factor 1 and 2 (FGF1 and FGF2), and platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), antimicrobial enzymes (e.g., lactoperoxidase), and whey proteins (e.g., lactalbumin), as well as other bioactive proteins identified through proteomic analyses (Hernandez-Castellano et al. 2014; McGrath et al., 2016; Kaçar and Batmaz 2023; Graydon et al. 2024; Stancheva and Penev, 2025). In addition to its antimicrobial and growth-supporting properties, colostrum represents the primary and most critical source of nutrition for the newborn calf. Colostrum supports both neonatal nutrition and immune protection; therefore, calves must receive sufficient amounts of high-quality colostrum as early as possible after birth to ensure adequate passive immune transfer and survival (Weaver et al., 2000; Godden et al., 2019).

The absorption of maternal immunoglobulins from colostrum into the bloodstream of the calf within the first 24 hours after birth, providing temporary protection against common infectious diseases until the calf's immature immune system becomes functionally active, is defined as passive transfer immunity (PTI) (Weaver et al., 2000; Blum, 2006). If calves fail to receive sufficient amounts of high-quality colostrum or if colostrum feeding is delayed, passive transfer becomes inadequate, a condition defined as failure of passive transfer (FPT). In practical terms, this condition is commonly defined as a serum IgG concentration below 1000 mg dL⁻¹ (10 g L⁻¹) in calves at 24 - 48 hours of age (Weaver et al., 2000; Lombard et al., 2020; Lichtmannsperger et al., 2023).

FPT is widely recognized as a major challenge in neonatal calf rearing systems. Despite improvements in colostrum management and herd health practices, inadequate passive immunity continues to be reported across different production systems and geographical regions. It has been suggested that approximately one out of every three calves worldwide may experience insufficient passive transfer under field conditions (Weaver et al., 2000). In Türkiye, available data indicate a comparable situation, suggesting that FPT remains a relevant and ongoing issue in calf health management. This condition is associated with increased susceptibility to disease, higher mortality rates, and reduced growth performance in calves (Beam et al., 2009; Topal et al., 2018; Kara and Ceylan, 2021; Lichtmannsperger et al., 2023).

This review aims to provide a concise and critical overview of passive transfer immunity in calves, with particular emphasis on evaluating colostrum management practices, discussing commonly used diagnostic

approaches and their practical interpretation, and highlighting evidence-based herd-level strategies to improve passive transfer success under field conditions.

This narrative review is based on previously published studies retrieved from electronic databases including PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Relevant original articles and review papers focusing on passive transfer immunity, colostrum management, and neonatal calf health were considered, with preference given to studies providing clinically applicable and up-to-date information.

Colostrum Quality as the Primary Determinant of PTI

The primary determinant of successful passive transfer immunity (PTI) is the ingestion of high-quality colostrum. For effective passive transfer, colostrum must be not only rich in immunoglobulins but also hygienically adequate. The quality of colostrum is influenced by multiple factors, including dry period length, parity, age, breed, and nutritional status of the dam (Weaver et al., 2000; Godden et al., 2019; Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

Parity is a key determinant, as multiparous cows generally produce colostrum with higher immunoglobulin concentrations, whereas primiparous animals tend to have lower IgG levels. Breed differences are also evident; beef breeds typically produce higher-quality colostrum than dairy breeds, while Holstein cows are often associated with lower IgG concentrations. Therefore, ensuring the use of high-quality colostrum is particularly critical, especially in dairy breeds such as Holsteins. In addition, maternal nutrition during late gestation plays a critical role, as inadequate energy and protein intake may negatively affect colostrum quality. Proper dry period management is also essential, as the dry period should neither be shorter than approximately 40 days nor prolonged beyond 90 days, since both conditions may adversely affect colostrum quality (Weaver et al., 2000; Godden et al., 2019; Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

Colostrum is generally considered to be of good quality when it contains approximately 50 g L⁻¹ of IgG, while concentrations around 60 g L⁻¹ are regarded as optimal. In addition to immunoglobulin concentration, physical quality should also be considered; colostrum used for feeding should be free of visible abnormalities such as blood contamination, clots, or signs of mastitis. High-quality colostrum is typically characterized by a thick, viscous consistency, a dark yellow coloration, and a creamy texture (Batmaz, 2021; Godden et al., 2019; Stancheva and Penev, 2025)

In practical field conditions, Brix refractometry is widely used to estimate colostrum quality; values above approximately 22 - 23 % correspond to about 50 g L⁻¹ IgG and are considered acceptable, whereas values of 27 % or higher correspond to approximately 60 g L⁻¹ IgG and indicate higher-quality colostrum (Bielmann et al., 2010; Bartier et al., 2015; Kaçar and Batmaz, 2023).

Hygienic quality is another essential component of colostrum quality. Colostrum is generally considered hygienic when the total bacterial count is below 100,000 cfu mL⁻¹ and coliform counts are below 10,000 cfu mL⁻¹ (Kaçar et al., 2025; Godden et al., 2019). Poor hygienic conditions can reduce immunoglobulin absorption and increase the risk of early-life infections. Furthermore, colostrum may serve as a potential source of pathogen transmission, including Bovine Leukemia Virus, *Mycobacterium bovis*, and *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis*; therefore, the use of colostrum obtained from disease-free animals or the use of pasteurized colostrum is of critical importance (Stabel, 2008; Godden et al., 2019; Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

Additional management-related factors may also influence colostrum quality. Colostrum leakage prior to calving can significantly reduce immunoglobulin concentration, leading to lower-quality colostrum. Moreover, excessively high colostrum yield at first milking (e.g., ≥ 8.5 L) is generally associated with dilution of immunoglobulins and consequently lower colostrum quality. The health status of the dam-particularly the presence

of mastitis-may compromise colostrum quality by altering its composition and reducing immunoglobulin content. In contrast, the immunological status of the dam, including prior exposure to pathogens and vaccination programs during late gestation, may positively influence colostrum quality by enhancing immunoglobulin content and specificity. Therefore, both immunological and hygienic quality of colostrum must be considered together to ensure successful passive transfer (Weaver et al., 2000; Godden et al., 2019).

Timing of Colostrum Feeding

The timing of colostrum feeding is a critical factor affecting the success of passive transfer immunity (PTI). Colostrum absorption in neonatal calves is highest immediately after birth and is influenced by several physiological factors, including relatively low abomasal acidity due to insufficient hydrochloric acid secretion, limited pancreatic digestive enzyme activity, the presence of trypsin inhibitors in colostrum, and increased intestinal permeability during the early postnatal period (Şentürk, 2018; Godden et al., 2019).

The efficiency of immunoglobulin absorption is maximal within the first 4 - 6 hours after birth, decreases progressively after 6 - 12 hours, and falls below 10 % after 24 hours (Blum and Hammon, 2000; Chigerwe et al., 2009). This decline is primarily attributed to the process of intestinal closure, during which enterocytes progressively lose their ability to absorb large macromolecules such as immunoglobulins (Blum and Hammon, 2000; Weaver et al., 2000).

Therefore, colostrum should be administered as soon as possible after birth, preferably within the first 2 hours of life, to maximize immunoglobulin absorption and ensure successful passive transfer. After the first 24 hours, although the systemic absorption of immunoglobulins becomes minimal, colostrum feeding may still contribute to local intestinal immunity and help prevent colonization and proliferation of enteric pathogens (Conneely et al., 2014; Godden et al., 2019; Parreno et al., 2010). These findings emphasize that timely colostrum administration is a decisive factor in maximizing immunoglobulin absorption and achieving effective passive transfer in neonatal calves.

Amount of Colostrum Intake

Adequate passive transfer immunity (PTI) depends not only on timely colostrum administration but also on the ingestion of sufficient amounts of immunoglobulins. To achieve adequate PTI, calves should absorb approximately 150 - 200 g of IgG, which is generally associated with a minimum serum IgG concentration of 1000 mg dL⁻¹. Considering that high-quality colostrum typically contains around 50 g L⁻¹ of IgG, calves should consume approximately 3 - 4 L at first feeding to meet immunoglobulin requirements (Godden et al., 2019; Batmaz, 2021; Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

A substantial proportion of the required immunoglobulin mass (approximately 100 g IgG) should be provided during this first feeding, when intestinal absorption efficiency is at its peak. Current evidence indicates that feeding 8.5 - 10 % of body weight (approximately 3 - 4 L for an average Holstein calf) within the first 1 - 2 hours after birth significantly improves passive transfer success (Conneely et al., 2014; Stancheva and Penev, 2025). Weaver et al. (2000) similarly recommended the administration of approximately 4 L of high-quality colostrum shortly after birth, particularly when natural suckling is inadequate.

A second colostrum feeding of approximately 2 L within the first 8 - 12 hours of life is recommended to further increase total IgG intake and improve serum IgG concentrations (Godden et al., 2019; Stancheva and Penev, 2025). Earlier recommendations suggested that calves should receive approximately 10 % of their body weight in

colostrum within the first 24 hours and at least 5 % within the first 2 hours after birth (Şentürk, 2018); however, current evidence supports higher initial feeding volumes (8.5 - 10 % of body weight within the first 1 - 2 hours after birth) as more effective for achieving optimal passive transfer (Conneely et al., 2014; Stancheva and Penev, 2025). These findings collectively indicate that both sufficient colostrum volume and early administration are essential to ensure successful passive transfer.

Assessment of Passive Transfer Immunity

The evaluation of passive transfer immunity (PTI) in calves can be performed using several diagnostic methods. The gold standard approach is the direct measurement of serum IgG concentrations using laboratory methods such as radial immunodiffusion (RID) or ELISA. However, these methods are relatively expensive, require well-equipped laboratories, and are time-consuming, which often limits their routine use on an individual-animal basis under field conditions. Therefore, semiquantitative tests that are more practical for field use and have been shown to correlate with serum IgG concentrations are also widely utilized (Weaver et al., 2000; Topal et al., 2018; Godden et al., 2019).

Accordingly, indirect and semiquantitative tests, including Brix refractometry, total protein measurement, sodium sulfate turbidity, zinc sulfate turbidity, serum gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) activity, and the glutaraldehyde coagulation test are widely used under field conditions for this purpose, as they provide rapid, cost-effective, and practical alternatives with well-established cut-off values and reliable performance in field applications. However, potential influencing factors such as hydration status and non-Ig protein fractions should be taken into account when interpreting results. Therefore, although laboratory-based methods provide higher analytical accuracy, the selection of diagnostic tools in field conditions should be based on a balance between accuracy, feasibility, and cost.

Passive transfer status is typically evaluated between 24 and 48 hours after birth, with 48 hours considered the most reliable time point, as immunoglobulin absorption is largely completed by this time (Godden et al., 2019; Stancheva and Penev, 2025). At 48 hours of age, a serum IgG concentration ≥ 1000 mg dL⁻¹ is considered indicative of adequate passive transfer, whereas values ≥ 2000 mg dL⁻¹ are associated with very good passive transfer status. Similarly, serum total protein concentrations ≥ 5.5 g dL⁻¹ indicate adequate passive transfer, while values ≥ 6.0 g dL⁻¹ are considered very good. Brix refractometer readings ≥ 8.5 % are generally accepted as indicative of adequate passive transfer, whereas values ≥ 9.0 % reflect very good passive transfer status (Weaver et al., 2000; Topal et al., 2018; Aydoğdu et al., 2019; Batmaz et al., 2019; Giammarco et al., 2021; Akköse et al., 2022). For indirect coagulation-based assessments, glutaraldehyde coagulation times < 10 minutes suggest adequate passive transfer, while values < 5 minutes are associated with very good passive transfer. In addition, serum GGT activity > 500 IU L⁻¹ is considered adequate, whereas values > 1000 IU L⁻¹ indicate very good passive transfer (Topal et al., 2018; Batmaz et al., 2019; Batmaz, 2021). While these thresholds are generally interpreted based on measurements obtained around 48 hours of age, serum GGT activity can also be evaluated using age-specific reference values in the early neonatal period. Accordingly, serum GGT concentrations exceeding approximately 200 IU L⁻¹ at 1 day of age, 100 IU L⁻¹ at 4 days, and 75 IU L⁻¹ at 1 week are considered indicative of sufficient passive transfer. In contrast, values below 50 IU/L within the first two weeks of life are suggestive of failure of passive transfer (Weaver et al., 2000).

For herd-level evaluation, serum samples obtained at approximately 48 hours of age are recommended. If more than 20 % of calves have serum total protein concentrations below 5.5 g dL⁻¹ or Brix values below 8.5 %, this should be considered an alarm threshold indicating inadequate passive transfer at the herd level (Batmaz, 2021).

These diagnostic approaches, when applied using standardized cut-off values at approximately 48 hours of age, represent essential and reliable tools for both individual assessment and herd-level decision-making in calf health management.

Practical Implications and Recommendations

Passive transfer immunity (PTI) is a critical determinant of neonatal calf health, and its success depends on proper colostrum management. Effective implementation of the “Three Qs” concept-quality, quantity, and quick administration-remains the cornerstone of successful passive transfer (Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

High-quality colostrum ($\geq 50 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ IgG; Brix $\geq 22\text{--}23 \%$) should be provided as soon as possible after birth, ideally within the first 2 hours of life. Calves should receive approximately 3 - 4 L of colostrum (8.5 - 10 % of body weight) at the first feeding, followed by an additional feeding within the first 8–12 hours to ensure sufficient immunoglobulin intake (Weaver et al., 2000; Batmaz, 2021; Stancheva and Penev, 2025). Colostrum quality should be routinely assessed using practical tools such as Brix refractometry; in the absence of such measurements, colostrum with a thick consistency and dark yellow coloration should be preferentially selected. Colostrum containing visible blood clots, pus, or signs of mastitis should not be used.

Monitoring passive transfer status at approximately 48 hours of age is essential for evaluating the effectiveness of colostrum management. Practical on-farm tools such as Brix refractometry and serum total protein measurement can be reliably used for this purpose. Herd-level evaluation should also be performed: if more than 20% of calves fall below established threshold values (serum Brix $<8.5 \%$ and serum total protein $<5.5 \text{ g dL}^{-1}$), corrective management strategies should be implemented (Weaver et al., 2000; Batmaz, 2021).

In herds with a high prevalence of failure of passive transfer (FPT), a systematic evaluation approach should be adopted to identify and correct underlying causes. First, colostrum quality should be carefully assessed, as inadequate quality is one of the most common causes of FPT under field conditions. If quality is poor, factors such as dry period management, maternal nutrition, and the presence of immunosuppressive conditions (e.g., enzootic bovine leukosis, tuberculosis, or mycotoxicosis) should be investigated. If colostrum quality is adequate, attention should shift to management practices, including whether calves are actually fed colostrum, the volume administered, and the timing of feeding after birth (Şentürk, 2018; Weaver et al., 2000; Godden et al., 2019).

Excess high-quality colostrum should be properly stored for future use (McGuirk and Collins, 2004; Stewart et al., 2005; Denholm, 2022). First-milking colostrum should be frozen in clean containers, preferably in portions not exceeding 2 L, to facilitate rapid thawing and minimize the risk of microbial contamination. Frozen colostrum should be thawed using warm water (approximately 40 - 50 °C) in a water bath (bain-marie) method. The use of boiling water or microwave heating should be avoided, as exposure to high temperatures may cause denaturation of immunoglobulins and reduce colostral IgG activity and effectiveness (Denholm, 2022; Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

Alternative strategies such as colostrum replacers, IgG supplements, or hyperimmune serum preparations may be considered when maternal colostrum is insufficient or unavailable. Routine monitoring of colostrum intake at the calf level is also essential to ensure compliance with feeding protocols (Godden et al., 2019). In calves born to primiparous heifers, colostrum quality is often suboptimal; therefore, the use of high-quality colostrum obtained from multiparous cows within the herd is recommended. Similarly, for calves born from newly purchased pregnant animals, using stored colostrum originating from the resident herd may help enhance protection against farm-specific pathogens.

Maintaining strict hygiene during colostrum collection and handling is essential to preserve immunoglobulin functionality and minimize bacterial interference with absorption. The use of heat-treated colostrum (60 °C for 60 min) has been shown to reduce bacterial contamination while largely preserving immunoglobulin activity, thereby supporting safer and more effective passive transfer (Godden et al., 2006; Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

Even when colostrum quality, quantity, and timing are appropriate, FPT may still occur due to calf-related factors. Conditions such as dystocia, perinatal hypoxia, and metabolic acidosis may impair intestinal function and reduce the efficiency of immunoglobulin absorption. Therefore, calves experiencing difficult births or compromised vitality should be closely monitored and managed more intensively in the early postnatal period (Weaver et al., 2000; Godden et al., 2019; Stancheva and Penev, 2025).

Conclusion

In conclusion, optimizing colostrum quality, ensuring timely and adequate intake, and routinely monitoring passive transfer status-as part of a multifactorial approach that includes management practices, hygiene, and calf-related factors-are essential strategies to reduce neonatal morbidity and mortality and to improve overall herd health and productivity. Effective colostrum management is a key determinant of successful passive transfer in calves.

Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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